

Effects Of Training of Academic Staff on Employees' Performance in Federal Polytechnics, Nigeria

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Abstract:

This Study examines the effects of Training of Academic Staff on employees' Performance in the Federal Polytechnic, Kaura Namoda, Nigeria. This survey research has three questions to contend with. These questions gave rise to the three objectives of the study. To examine the effects of Training of Academic Staff on: employees' Productivity, Timeliness and Work quality respectively. It is equally hypothesized that there's no significant effect of Training of Academic Staff on employees' Productivity, Timeliness and Work quality respectively. A structured, close-ended questionnaire with a 5-point Likert scale was adopted to get data from the respondents. A total of 220 copies of the questionnaires were randomly administered using a stratified random sampling technique across the 7 schools as well as the library unit of the Polytechnic. Ordinary Least Square (O.L.S) method of regression and ANOVA methods of analysis were employed in analyzing the results with the aid of an SPSS computer package. Findings revealed that the Training of Academic Staff has a significant effect on employees' productivity, enhanced timeliness in service delivery and work quality. Additionally, there is a long list of staff waiting for sponsorship. The study recommends, among other issues for the periodic re-training of staff bearing in mind the dynamics of human activities. However, in doing that, beneficiaries of training programs should be made to serve the institution for a longer period than is presently being practiced

Keywords: Training, Employees Performance, Productivity, Timeliness, Work Quality and Career Development.

1. INTRODUCTION

Organizations are encountering increased competition owing to globalization, transformations in technology, political and economic environments (Evans, Pucik & Barsoux, 2002 cited in Tukunimulongo, 2016) and therefore prompting these organizations to train their employees as one of the ways to prepare them to adjust to the dynamics of time to enhance their performance becomes imperative (Tukunimulongo, 2016). It is important not to ignore the prevailing evidence on the growth of knowledge in the business corporate world in the last decade. This growth has not only been brought about by improvements in technology nor a combination of factors of production but increased efforts towards development of organizational human resources. It is, therefore, the responsibility of every organization to enhance the job performance of the employees and certainly the implementation of training and development is one of the major steps that most institutions or companies need to achieve this. As is evident that employees are a crucial resource, it is important to optimize the contribution of employees to the company's aims and goals as a means of sustaining effective performance. This demand for managers to confirm an acceptable supply of staff that is technically and socially capable and talented career development into high-quality departments or management positions (Sultana, Irum, Ahmed & Mehmood, 2012).

The question that may arise in many instances is why human resources are important. Bearing in mind that human resources are the intellectual property of the firm, employees prove to be a good source of gaining competitive advantage, according to Houger (2006), and training is the only way of developing organizational intellectual property through building employees' competencies. In order to succeed, organizations have to obtain and utilize human resources effectively (Houger, 2006). Organizations, therefore, need to design its human resources management in ways that fit into the organization's structure as this will make the organizations achieve their goals and objectives. Moreover, it is also important for organizations to assist their workforce in obtaining the necessary skills needed and increase commitment. The management of human resources in Africa in general and Nigeria in particular is rather challenging as most organizations have difficulties finding the right caliber of human resources. This may partly be a result of the different kinds of problems, for example, political instability, corruption, bureaucracy, poor infrastructure, low levels of education and purchasing power, diseases and famine known to prevail in the African continent (Kamoche, 2002).

To develop the desired knowledge, skills and abilities of the employees, to perform well on the job, requires effective training programs that may also affect employee motivation and commitment (Asaju, 2008). In order to prepare their workers to do their jobs as desired, organizations provide training so as to optimize their employees' potential. Most firms, by applying long term planning, invest in building new skills by their workforce, enabling them to cope with the uncertain conditions that they may face in the future, thus, improving the employees' performance through superior level of motivation and commitment. When employees recognize that their organization has interest in them through offering training programs, they in turn apply their best efforts to achieve organizational goals, and show high performance in their jobs.

Employees are the most valuable asset of any company or institution as they can make or break a company's or institution's reputation and can adversely affect profitability or the attainment of set goals. Employees often are responsible for the great bulk of the necessary work to be done as well as customer satisfaction and the quality of products or services and events. Without proper training, employees, both new and old do not receive the

information and develop the skill sets necessary for accomplishing their tasks at their maximum potential. Employees who undergo proper training tend to keep their jobs longer than those who do not. Training is a necessity in the workplace. Without it, employees do not have a firm grasp on their responsibilities or duties. Employee training refers to programs that provide workers with information, new skills, or professional development opportunities.

According to Byrne (2011), managers are trying their very best to develop employees' capabilities, ultimately creating a good working environment within the organization. In order to meet with the global educational standard in the Federal Polytechnic, Kaura Namoda, Nigeria, the management is involved in developing effective training and educational programs for its academic staff members to equip them with the desired knowledge, skills and abilities to achieve institutional goals. This line of action by the top management would not only improve the academic staff performance, but also create positive image of the institution.

Thus, effective training programs help the academic staff of the polytechnic to get acquainted with new technological advancements, and to gain full command of the competencies and skills required to perform at a particular job and to avoid on the job errors and mistakes. Amongst the important functions of human resources management, is employee development through proper training and development programs. This study looks at the effects of Training of Academic staff on employees' Performance in Federal Polytechnic, Kaura Namoda, Nigeria.

Statement of the Problem

The massive employment of staff in 2012/13 was unprecedented in the history of the Federal Polytechnic, Kaura Namoda, Nigeria. The challenges posed by new employees can be very costly. The implication of such a line of action on the performances of the school was great to say the least. Many of the newly employed academic staff could not find their bearing in the roles expected of them. This led to poor student performance. Less than average performance of students in recent times, in spite of all the training programs instituted by the school with the aim of improving the academic staff quality was a matter of concern to all and sundry.

This study stems out of the realization of the need to examine the effects of Training of Academic Staff on employees' performance bearing in mind the huge amounts being invested in training programs by the polytechnic over the years.

Furthermore, the inconsistency in the existing empirical literature (Abeeha & Bariha, 2012; Ahmed & Tsafe, 2013) makes it inevitable to seek for more evidences on the effects of Training of Academic Staff on employees' Performance in the Federal Polytechnic, Kaura Namoda, Nigeria.

The lacuna created by the non-contextualization of the effects of Training of Academic Staff on employees' Performance with specific reference to Federal Polytechnic, Kaura Namoda, Nigeria, will be bridged by this study.

Research Questions

The following research questions are raised with a view to achieving the objectives of the study:

- i. What is the effect of Training of Academic staff on employees' Productivity in Federal Polytechnic, Kaura Namoda, Nigeria?
- ii. What is the effect of Training of Academic staff on employees' Timeliness in Federal Polytechnic, Kaura Namoda, Nigeria?
- iii. What is the effect of Training of Academic staff on employees' Work quality in Federal Polytechnic, Kaura Namoda, Nigeria?

Objectives of the Study

The main objective of this study is to examine the effects of Training of Academic Staff on employees' Performance in Federal Polytechnic, Kaura Namoda. The specific objectives are to:

- i. Examine the effect of Training of Academic staff on employees' Productivity in Federal Polytechnic, Kaura Namoda, Nigeria.
- ii. Assess the effect of Training of Academic staff on employees' Timeliness in Federal Polytechnic, Kaura Namoda, Nigeria.
- iii. Evaluate the effect of Training of Academic staff on employees' Work quality in Federal Polytechnic, Kaura Namoda, Nigeria.

Statement of the Hypotheses

Based on the objectives of the study, the following hypotheses are postulated:

H₀₁: There is no significant effect of Training of Academic staff on employees' Productivity in Federal Polytechnic, Kaura Namoda, Nigeria.

H₀₂: There is no significant effect of Training of Academic staff on employees' Timeliness in Federal Polytechnic, Kaura Namoda, Nigeria.

H₀₃: There is no significant effect of Training of Academic staff on employees' Work quality in Federal Polytechnic, Kaura Namoda, Nigeria.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

Concept of Training

Effective training and development programs are aimed at improving the employees' performances. Training refers to bridging the gap between the current performance and the standard desired performance. Training could be given through different methods such as on the job coaching and mentoring, peer cooperation and participation by the subordinates. This team work enable employees actively participate on the job and produces better performance, hence improving organizational performance. Training programs not only develops employees, but also help an organization to make good use of their human resources in favor of gaining competitive advantage. Therefore, it seems mandatory for the firm to plan for such a training program for its employees to enhance their abilities and competencies that are needed at the workplace, (Deborah & Ofori, 2006).

According to Waleed (2011), as cited in Ng'ethe, (2014) training is not simply a means of arming employees with the skills they need to perform their jobs it is often deemed to be representative of an employer's commitment to their workforce. However, it is important to point out that human resources (HR) practices work to develop individual knowledge and skills, as well as employee attitude and behaviors. If these effects are prevalent enough in the employees' population, then the collective changes in human capital, attitudes, behaviors and associated organizational climate would be strong enough to influence organizational performance (Eleve, 2012).

Training not only develops the capabilities of the employee, but sharpen their thinking ability and creativity in order to make better decisions in time and in a more productive manner (Harvey, 2002). Moreover, it also enables employees to deal with the customer in an effective manner and respond to their complaints in time (Harvey, Myers & Novicevic, 2002). The training develops self-efficacy and results in superior performance on jobs (Svenja, 2007), by replacing the traditional work practices by efficient and effective work related practices (Kathiravan, Devadason & Zakkeer, 2006). Training refers to a planned intervention aimed at enhancing the elements of individual job performance (Chiaburu & Tekleab, 2005).

Importance of Training

Training is important and an imperative tool for the organization to revamp the performance of all the personnel for organizational growth and success (Svenja, 2007). It is useful to both employers and employees of an establishment. An employee will become more efficient and productive if he is trained well. Organizations can improve and increase the quality of the existing employees by providing thorough training and development. Training is essential not only to increase productivity but also to motivate and inspire workers by letting them know how important their jobs are and giving them all the information they need to perform those jobs (Herman & Kurt, 2016). The overall benefits obtained from employee training are: increased motivation, increased job satisfaction and morale, increased efficiencies in processes, resulting in financial gain, increased capacity to adopt new technologies and methods, increased innovation in strategies and products and reduced employee turnover.

Methods of Training

Jackson (2002) noted that all the human resources development activities are meant to either improve performance on the present job of the individual, train new skills for a new job or a new position in the future and general growth for both individuals and organization so as to be able to meet an organization's current and future objectives. There are broadly two different methods that organizations may choose from for training and developing skills of its employees. These are *on-the-job training* given to organizational employees while conducting their regular work at the same working venues and *off-the-job training* involves taking employees away from their usual work environments and therefore the trainees concentrates on the training. Examples of the *on-the-job training* include, but are not limited to, job rotations and transfers, coaching and or mentoring. On the other hand, *off-the-job training* examples include: conferences, role playing, and many more. Armstrong (2013) argues that on-the-job training may consist of teaching or coaching by more experienced people or trainers at the desk or at the bench. Different organizations are motivated to take on different training methods for a number of reasons for example; (1) depending on the organization's strategy, goals and resources available, (2) depending on the needs identified at the time, and (3) the target group to be trained which may include among others individual workers, groups, teams, department or the entire organization.

Job Rotation and Transfers: Job rotation and transfers according to Jeremic, Jovanovic and Gasevi (2003), is a way of developing employee skills within the organization and involves movements of employees from one official responsibility to another, for example, taking on the higher rank position within the organization, or from one branch of the organization to another. For transfers, for example, it could involve movement of employees from one country to another. These rotations and transfers facilitate employees to acquire knowledge of the different operations within the organization together with the differences existing in different countries where the organization operates. The knowledge acquired by the selected employees for this method is beneficial to the organization as it may increase the competitive advantage of the organization.

Concept of Employee Performance

According to Hawthorne studies and many other research works on the productivity of workers, highlighted the fact that employees who are satisfied with their jobs will have higher job performance, and thus supreme job

retention, than those who are not happy with their jobs (Irene, 2009). Moreover, it is stated that employees are more likely to turnover if they are not satisfied and hence less motivated to show good performance. Employee performance is higher in happy and satisfied workers and the management finds it easy to motivate high performers to attain firm targets. (Kinicki & Kreitner; 2007) The employee could be only satisfied when they feel themselves competent to perform their jobs, which is achieved through better training programs.

Relationship between Training and Employees' Performance

Most of the previous studies provide the evidence that there is a strong positive relationship between human resource management practices and organizational performance (Purcell, Kinnie, Hutchinson, Rayton & Swart, 2003). According to Michael (2008), mentioned in his study that training and development program, as one of the vital human resources management practice, positively affects the quality of the workers' knowledge, skills and capability and thus results in higher employee performance on the job. This relationship ultimately contributes to superior organizational performance. The result of a study by Muna, Iravo and Omondi (2011), depicts the positive correlation between training and employee performance as $r=.233$. Thus, we can predict from this finding that it is not possible for the firm to gain higher returns without properly utilizing its human resources. This can only happen when a firm is able to meet its employees' job related needs in a timely manner. Training is the only way of identifying the deprived need of employees and then building their required competence level so that they may perform well to achieve organizational goals. Studies by Sultan, el tal (2012), conducted in the telecom sector of Pakistan, states the R^2 as .501 which means that 50.1% of variation in employee performance is brought by training programs. Furthermore, the T-value was 8.58 that explain training is the best predictor of employee performance. As depicted by the work of Harrison (2000), learning through training influence the organizational performance by greater employee performance, and is said to be a key factor in the achievement of corporate goals. However, implementing training programs as a solution to covering performance issues such as filling the gap between the standard and the actual performance is an effective way of improving employee performance (Swart, et al., 2005).

According to Swart, Mann, Brown and Price (2005), bridging the performance gap refers to implementing a relevant training intervention for the sake of developing particular skills and abilities of the workers and enhancing employee performance. He further elaborates the concept by stating that training facilitates organization to recognize that its workers are not performing well and a thus their knowledge, skills and attitudes needs to be molded according to the firm needs. There might be various reasons for poor performance of the employees such as workers may not feel motivated anymore to use their competencies, or maybe not confident enough in their capabilities, or they may be facing work-life conflict. All the above aspects must be considered by the firm while selecting most appropriate training intervention that helps organizations to solve all problems and enhance employee motivational level to participate and meet firm expectations by showing desired performance. As mentioned by Swart, et al.,(2005), thus employee, superior performance occur only because of good quality training programs that leads to employee motivation and their needs fulfilled. Wright and Geroy (2001) observed that employee competencies change through effective training programs. It not only improves the overall performance of the employees to effectively perform the current job, but also enhance the knowledge, skills and attitude of the workers necessary for the future job, thus contributing to superior organizational performance. Through training the employee competencies are developed and enable them to implement job related work efficiently, and achieve firm objectives in a competitive manner.

However, employee performance is also affected by some environmental factors such as corporate culture, organizational structure, job design, performance appraisal systems, power and politics prevailing in the firm and the group dynamics. If the above mentioned problems exist in the firm, employee performance decreases not due to lack of relevant knowledge, skills and attitude, but because of the above mentioned hurdles. To make training effective and to ensure positive effect of training on employee performance these elements should be taken into consideration (Wright & Geroy 2001). Lisa and Holly (2007), stated that workers feel more committed to the firm, when they feel an organizational commitment towards them and thus show higher performance.

Kum, Cowded and Karodia (2014), reports that there is a positive correlation between effective training program and employee productivity, however, to make it possible, Swart, et al., (2005), said it is the responsibility of the managers to identify the factors that hinders training program effectiveness and should take necessary measures to neutralize their effect on employee performance. In addition, Kamoche, Yaw, Frank and Gerry (2004) concluded that high levels of employee commitment is achieved if training, achieves learning outcomes and improves the performance, both on individual and organizational level. These findings are also consistent with the results of Kim's (2006) research work. Generally, it can be debated that the effect of the training program on employee outcomes such as motivation, job satisfaction and organizational commitment, did not receive much attention so far. A rare work was done to test whether firms can affect their workers' attitude, through proper training interventions. According to Ngome (2010), training should be planned in such a way that examined results in organizational commitment. On the other hand Gaertner and Nollen (2009) proposed that employees' commitment is a result of some human resources practices, that is, succession planning and promotions, career development and training opportunities. All these practices, when achieved results in greater employee performance. Moreover, Meyer and Smith (2000) the link between human resource management practices and organizational commitment, so as to discover the causes of effective employee performance.

Although the above literature provides the evidences regarding the benefits of training and its positive influence on employee performance, Cheramie, et al., (2007), argued that, management most at times feel hesitant while investing in its human resources due to various reasons. Sometimes, in spite of receiving effective and timely training programs, some employees try to cash it for the sake of their own market value and employment opportunity or willing to change jobs just because of higher salaries, and thus, firm investment in training results as a cost rather than profit. It is also observed that due to the resistance of the organization towards offering training, this will compel individuals to invest in themselves for their career development and greater performance (Baruch, 2006).

As mentioned by Ngome (2010), training sessions accelerate the initiative, ability and creativity of the workforce and facilitate to avoid human resource obsolescence that may occur because of demographic factors such as age, attitude or the inability to cope with changes. Obisi (2001), reported that training is a systematic process of enhancing the knowledge, skills and attitude, hence leads to satisfactory performance by the employees at work. He further mentioned that the need and objectives of the training program should be identified before offering it to the employees.

Kraak, (2005), argued that training is the crux of better organizational management, as it makes employees more efficient and effective. They further elaborated that training practices have a strong bond with all other human resources practices as postulated by Kamoche, (2002), it enables employees to develop themselves within the firm and raise their market value in the market. Moreover, training supports to shape employees' job related behavior and facilitate them to participate for the success of the organization and ultimately the firm gets higher return due to superior performance of its employees. Kraak (2005) further mentioned that a well-trained worker is able to make the best use of organizational resources along with a minimum level of wastages. As stated by Niazi (2011), when employees are well trained organization can delegate responsibility and authority to them with full confidence of ensuring organizational success.

Rao (2011) suggests the need for renewed attention to employee training due to its ability to cut costs and reduce performance shortfalls in organizations. It has been proven on countless occasions that, there is a strong link between various training and development practices and organizational performance (Raja, Furgan, & Muhammad, 2011). Research has found training as a tool for cost cutting and value creation in organizations (Kraak, 2005). Similarly, training facilitates the achievement of corporate strategy and improves organizational performance, especially for learning organizations (Quarty, 2012). So training must be aligned with organizational strategy in order to result in high performance in those organizations. Further, a study focusing on the impact of training on organizational performance reveals that, only off-the job training improves performance, whereas on-the-job training does not (Kamoche, 2002). Additionally, Gareth (2003) argued that, general training has a positive impact on firm performance, whereas firm-specific training does not.

Often in implicit findings, Niazi, (2011), argued that training increases employees' propensity to perform and subsequently contributes to the firms' performance. For example, Rao (2011), was of the view that those companies (citing Jaguar Cars; Lucas Industries; IBM; Marks & Spencer; British steel; & Nissan) that integrated training and development practices into their business planning enhances their own performance. A study by Niazi (2011) revealed that organizations that are committed to quality investment in training and development of its employees receive an exponential growth in customer delights, profitability and overall economic growth of those organizations. There is a huge return on those training investments (ROI). Gareth (2003), supported Niazi (2011) by adding that, those organizations that train employees reduce employee turnover rate. Kraak (2005), citing Bishop (1994), indicates that employer-provided training and development raises subjective productivity and performance measure by almost 16%.

Moreover, the above empirical findings suggest that organizations that train their employees consistently have better outcomes than those that do not. Quarty (2012) agreeing to the finding of Niazi (2011) indicates that training can be a powerful driving force for firm expansion as well as building capabilities too, and subsequently firms' profitability and productivity. In exploring the impact of training on enterprise growth, Jones, Richard, Paul and Peter (2008) confirms that increasing training efforts increases firms' growth in terms of sales volumes and revenues. In contrast, empirical findings on training and organizational performance are inconclusive. As some scholars bemoaned that, training does not necessarily impact performance. One divergent view comes from Kraak (2005) who found that the relationship between employee training and organizational performance is not significant. Other researchers like Niazi (2011), and Gaertner and Nollen (2009), also argued that there is a weak direct relationship between training and firm's performance. Obisi (2001), also claims that, training activities fail to influence the firm's performance because the activities are not linked to the firm's strategic plans. However, whether there is a strong or a weak link between these two concepts requires further contextual and empirical findings especially for industries and institutions in Nigeria.

In the improvement of groups, training plays a crucial role, improving overall performance in addition to increasing productivity, and subsequently setting groups within the fine role to face competition and live at the top. This approach that there is a giant difference among the agencies that train their personnel and groups that do not (Benedictta & Appiah, 2010). Training is a kind of interest which is deliberate, systematic and it effects in an greater degree of skill, information and competency which might be necessary to perform paintings successfully (Kraak 2005). There exists a high quality association among education and employee performance. Training generates blessings for the worker as well as for the company by means of positively influencing worker performance through the improvement of employee expertise, skills, capacity, competencies and conduct (Rao, 2011).

In the real world, organizational increase and improvement is suffering from a number of factors. In line with the prevailing studies throughout the improvement of businesses, worker schooling performs a essential function in improving overall performance in addition to increasing productiveness. This in turn ends in putting organizations within the quality positions to stand opposition and live at the pinnacle. This therefore implies the lifestyles of an enormous distinction between the agencies that educate their employees and organizations that do not. Existing literature provides evidence of the lifestyles of the obvious consequences of schooling and development on worker overall performance. Some studies have proceeded by way of looking at overall performance in terms of employee performance, particularly (Purcell, Kinnie & Hutchinson 2003; Harrison 2000), even as others have prolonged it to a standard outlook of organizational performance (Dessler, 1997; Swart, et al., 2005). In one way or the alternative, the two are related inside, the feel that employee overall performance is a characteristic of organizational performance since worker performance affects widespread organizational overall performance. In relation to the above, Wright and Geroy (2001), stated that employee skills trade through powerful training packages. It therefore not simplest improves the general performance of the personnel to effectively carry out their current jobs, but also complements the knowledge, capabilities and mind-set of the workers important for the destiny jobs, therefore contributing to advanced organizational performance.

Earlier research on training and employee overall performance has found interesting findings concerning this courting. Training has been validated to generate overall performance improvement associated blessings for the employee in addition to for the organization by using positively influencing employee performance via the improvement of worker expertise, capabilities, capacity, talents and behavior (Benedictta & Appiah, 2010; Harrison, 2000). Moreover, other studies, for instance, one through Swart,et al., (2005) problematic on education as a method of managing skill deficits and performance gaps as a way of enhancing employee performance. According to Swart, et al.,(2005), bridging the performance hole refers to enforcing a applicable training intervention for the sake of growing particular abilities and skills of the employees and enhancing worker overall performance. They further intricate the idea by means of declaring that schooling helps corporations to recognize that its workers aren't appearing well and as such their knowledge, skills and attitudes wishes to be molded in line with the company wishes. It is constantly in order that employees own a positive amount of knowledge related to one of a kind jobs. However, it is vital to notice that this isn't always enough and personnel want to constantly adapt to new necessities of activity performance. In other phrases, corporations want to have non-stop rules of schooling and retraining of personnel and as such do now not want to await occurrences of ability and overall performance gaps.

According to Wright and Geroy (2001), worker competencies exchange through powerful training programs. It no longer only improves the overall performance of the employees to successfully perform the contemporary job, but also beautifies the understanding, abilities and mindset of the people essential for the destiny activity, for that reason contributing to advanced organizational overall performance. Through schooling, employee capabilities are developed and permit them to put into effect the task associated work effectively, and reap company goals in a aggressive manner. Further nonetheless, dissatisfaction, court cases, absenteeism and turnover may be significantly decreased while personnel are so properly educated that they are able to revel in the direct delight associated with the experience of achievement and knowledge that they are growing their inherent capabilities (Kim, 2006).

Abay (2008) said that an extensive courting turned into determined among the worker training and their resultant performance in undertaking extraordinary obligations. It became found that the ones employees who've taken trainings were extra successful in performing unique assignment and vice versa. Training has an instantaneous courting with the personnel' job performance. Similar findings had been suggested by way of Elnegal and Imran (2013), Jagero and Komba (2012), Saeed and Asghar (2012), and, Singh and Mohanty (2012).

However, Jagero and Komba (2012) posited that while schooling is a thing in task overall performance, it's miles the combination of factors which includes working surroundings, employee abilities and information, motivation and rewards, conversation flow and organizational subculture that significantly improve personnel' overall performance. Herman and Kurt (2016), argued that worker schooling equip employees with competencies that enable them to become greater efficient and productive workers. Furthermore, personnel who're well-skilled frequently have higher motivation and morale because they sense that the company has invested of their capability and development. This also consequences in decrease turnover fees. Devins (2012), determined that trained personnel often paintings better as groups because anyone is aware about the expectancies and can obtain them together easily. Trained employees are also extra assured of their performance and selection-making skills. In addition, personnel who get hold of normal schooling are much more likely to simply accept change and give you new ideas.

Employees who learn new capabilities via training make desirable candidates for promotions due to the fact they have shown their capacity to learn, preserve and use facts. Reliable, professional personnel can also be empowered to educate different personnel, the fact that reduces strain for the management crew. Because of the real implications of schooling, it is crucial to have education this is powerful. Studies have demonstrated that greater costly, however powerful education can store money this is wasted on reasonably-priced, but inefficient education (Kenney, 2009).

Latif (2010) found four subscales to have a significant contribution towards the establishment of an effective training program. The study identified four factors to be contingent to an effective training, they were: Satisfaction with the training session, Training content satisfaction, Trainee satisfaction, and Transfer of learning.

Kennedy (2009) found that the frequency of training received has an impact on job performance. After analyzing data from employees of the Judicial Service of Ghana, he reported that many employees associated frequent in-service training with improved job performance. Similarly, Collen (2000), found a significant relationship between frequent on-the-job training and employees' performance. He stated that frequently training employees resulted in employees making fewer mistakes, getting more work done in a given time period and managers spending less time on supervision of employees.

However, Philips (2006), argued that loss of common training isn't necessarily the cause of below-performance of personnel. He said they want to decide whether a trouble may be solved via schooling. Whenever employees are not acting their jobs well, it's miles regularly assumed that education will convey them up to traditional. This is not usually the case. For example, training is less powerful for issues springing up from an employee's lack of motivation or lack of interest to the task. Similarly, Daniels (2010) posited that education is not a panacea; it cannot get rid of core troubles like low capitalization or a product line that doesn't meet clients' wishes. Although education can offer brilliant improvements in the organization, the key to getting the exceptional return on investment from training is to view it strategically instead of tactically. Adeniji (2002), in addition said that schooling reduces worker turnover and promotes purpose congruency whilst loss of education will increase absenteeism rate, low output, negative nice and results in high unit cost.

Despite the significance of training and manpower development in employee productivity and organizational performance, education programs aren't sufficiently supported via companies in Nigeria. These corporations keep in mind the cash they will spend on their education applications as waste instead of a funding. They fail to foresee the desirability of continuous schooling and improvement in their personnel if you want to sell the efficiency and effectiveness in their companies. Those that try and conduct trainings for their employees accomplish that in an ad-hoc and haphazard manner, and as such, schooling in the ones businesses is greater or less unplanned and unsystematic. This view is corroborated by Nwachukwu (1988), who argued that many personnel have failed in organizations because of lack of simple education

3. Material and Methods

The descriptive research design was used as a means of assessing the effects of Training of Academic Staff on employees' Performance in the Federal Polytechnic, Kaura Namoda, Nigeria.

Population and Sampling Technique

The population of the study is the 410 Academic staff of the Federal Polytechnic, Kaura Namoda. Yamane's (1973) sample size determination formula was used to determine the desired sample size of the research work.

Given the survey population (N) of 410, and making an allowance for error of 5 per cent, the sample size is determined at approximately 203 as worked below:

$$s = \frac{N}{1+N(ME)^2}$$

$$= \frac{410}{1+410(0.05)^2} = 2.025 = 203$$

Then, a stratified random sampling procedure was used to select the sample across the schools and the library unit that constitute the academic segments of the Polytechnic. The table below presents the stratified sample size randomly drawn from each of the 7 schools and the library unit.

Table 1 Population and Sample Size

Schools in Federal Polytechnic, Kaura Namoda, Nigeria	Population	Sample Size
School of Business and Management Studies (SBMS)	83	45
School of Engineering and Technology (SET)	56	30
School of Environmental Studies (SES)	37	20
School of Science and Technology (SST)	73	39
School of Information and Communication Technology (SICT)	66	35
School of General Studies (SGS)	70	38
School of Remedial and Basic Studies (SRBS)	17	09
Library Unit	8	04
TOTAL	410	220

Source; Establishment Office/ Researchers' Computation, 2016

Methods of Data Collection

This study utilized primary data collected basically through structured closed ended questionnaires of 5-point Likert scale format administered to the academic staff of the Federal Polytechnic, Kaura Namoda. Using a stratified random sampling method, 220 copies of the questionnaire were administered among the academic staff members of the Polytechnic. Out of this figure 205 were completed and returned, giving a response rate of 93.2%. The responses received are presented and analyzed below. The spread of the 205 completed and returned copies of the questionnaire is presented in table 2.

Table 2 Completed and Returned copies of questionnaire.

Schools in Federal Polytechnic, Kaura Namoda, Nigeria	Completed Questionnaire
School of Business and Management Studies (SBMS)	42
School of Engineering and Technology (SET)	28
School of Environmental Studies (SES)	18
School of Science and Technology (SST)	36
School of Information and Communication Technology (SICT)	33
School of General Studies (SGS)	36
School of Remedial and Basic Studies (SRBS)	08
Library Unit	04
TOTAL	205

Source; Researchers' Computation 2016

Table 2.1: Scale Reliability of Independent Variables

Concept/Independent Variables	Cronbach's Alpha
Enhancement	0.92
Job Knowledge	0.87
Skills	0.91
Competence	0.89
Morale	0.78

Source: Researcher's Computation, 2016

Table 2.1 above revealed that all the variables have Alpha Values above 0.6 mark recommended by Sekaran (2001). Therefore, all the variables in the instrument are deemed reliable.

Table 2.2: Scale Reliability of Dependent Variables

Concept/Dependent Variables	Cronbach's Alpha
Productivity	0.88
Timeliness	0.93
Work Quality	0.81

Source: Researcher's Computation, 2016

Table 2.2 above further revealed that all the variables have Alpha Values above 0.6 mark recommended by Sekaran (2001). Therefore, all the variables in the instrument are deemed as highly reliable. The researcher decided to continue with the study.

Procedures for Data Analysis and Model Specifications

Ordinary Least Squares Method of Regression was used with the aid of Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) to determine and analyze the effects of academic staff training on employees' performance. Thus, training was measured by Enhancement, Job knowledge, Skills, Competence and Morale as independent variables. The employee's performance was measured by Productivity, Timeliness and Work quality as dependent variables.

The Models for the Regression are:

PRDTY=F (Enhancement, Job Knowledge, Skills, Competence, Morale)

TIMLNS=F (Enhancement, Job Knowledge, Skills, Competence, Morale)

WQTY=F (Enhancement, Job Knowledge, Skills, Competence, Morale)

Mathematically,

PRDTY= $b_0 + \beta_1 \text{Enhancement} + \beta_2 \text{Job Knowledge} + \beta_3 \text{Skills} + \beta_4 \text{Competence} + \beta_5 \text{Morale} + \mu$

TIMLNS= $b_0 + \beta_1 \text{Enhancement} + \beta_2 \text{Job Knowledge} + \beta_3 \text{Skills} + \beta_4 \text{Competence} + \beta_5 \text{Morale} + \mu$

WQTY= $b_0 + \beta_1 \text{Enhancement} + \beta_2 \text{Job Knowledge} + \beta_3 \text{Skills} + \beta_4 \text{Competence} + \beta_5 \text{Morale} + \mu$

Where:

PRDTY=Productivity

TIMLNS=Timeliness

WQTY=Work Quality

b_0 =Intercept or Constant

β = Slope of the regression line with respect to the independent variables

μ =error term

Decision Rule

In order to estimate the regression analysis model, SPSS was used. The procedure involved specifying the independent and dependent variables; in this case, training (Enhancement, Job Knowledge, Skills, Competence, and Morale) are the independent variables while employees' performance (Productivity, Timeliness, and Work quality) are the dependent variables. SPSS was run and from the output, the values of the constant (b_0), coefficient of regression (β_1 - β_5) were obtained. In addition the outputs showed the T statistics and P- values for

the coefficients which resulted in either rejecting or failure to reject the hypotheses at 5% level of significance. The P- value is a probability of getting a result that is at least extremely as the critical values. The null hypotheses was rejected if the P-value is less than or equal to the critical value. Also, the outputs showed the coefficient of determination (r^2), which measured the proportion of the dependent variables that can be explained by the regression model. At the P-value of less than or equal to critical value the null hypothesis was rejected that there is a slope between the variables. The linear relationship exist when the P-value or significance level is less than or equal to the critical value.

4. DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS.

Training of Academic Staff and Employees’ Productivity.

Table 3: Responses on the Training of Academic Staff and Employees’ Productivity.

Response	Enhancement	Job Knowledge	Skills	Competence	Morale	Productivity	Total Frequency
Strongly Agree	99	128	145	121	152	134	779
Agree	90	61	50	62	43	62	368
Undecided	7	4	8	8	5	6	38
Disagree	6	8	2	9	4	1	30
Strongly Disagree	3	4	0	5	1	2	15
Total	205	205	205	205	205	205	1230

Source: Questionnaire administered 2016.

Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.963 ^a	.687	.563	2.38432

a. Predictors: (Constant), Enhancement, Job Knowledge, Skills, Competence and Morale.

ANOVA^b

Model		Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	171.422	5	28.255	24.347	.000 ^a
	Residual	105.401	199	1.176		
	Total	276.823	204			

a. Predictors: (Constant), Enhancement, Job Knowledge, Skills, Competence and Morale.

b. Dependent Variable: Productivity.

Summary of Regression Results and other Statistics.

Regression	A	β_1 Enhancmnt	β_2 JobKnw	β_3 Skills	β_4 Competence	β_4 Morale
Coefficient	-3.025	0.201	0.423	0.563	0.432	1.324
P. value	0.000	0.022	0.002	0.021	0.023	0.001
R	0.687					
r^2	0.563					

Source: Researcher’s Computation, 2016.

The regression line $Productivity = -3.025 + 0.201Enhancement + 0.423JobKnowledge + 0.563Skills + 0.432Competence + 1.324Morale$, indicates that employees’ productivity will increase by 0.201units for every 1unit increase in Enhancement, increase by 0.423 units for every 1unit increase in Job Knowledge, increase by 0.563 units for every 1unit increase in Skills, increase by 0.432units for every 1unit increase in Competence, and increase by 1.324units for every 1unit increase in Morale. The significant values or P-values of 0.022, 0.004, 0.021, 0.023, and 0.001, in all the respective variables are less than the t-value of 0.05. We, therefore, reject the Null Hypothesis and accept the Alternative Hypothesis, that the effect of training of Academic staff on employees’ productivity of Federal Polytechnic, Kaura Namoda is significant. This is collaborated by the correlation coefficient (r) of 0.963 that indicates a strong positive relationship. The coefficient of determination (r^2) of 0.687 indicates that 68.7% of variation on employees’ productivity can be explained by staff training. In the absence of training, it is indicated that employees’ productivity will reduce by 3.025 as shown by the constant (α). The F-Statistics value of 24.347 and its corresponding P-value of 0.000 also collaborate the rejection of the null hypothesis that the model is fit and the effects of Training of Academic staff on Employees’ Productivity is insignificant.

Training of Academic Staff and Employees’ Timeliness.

Table 3.1: Responses on the Training of Academic Staff and Employees’ Timeliness.

Response	Enhancement	Job Knowledge	Skills	Competence	Morale	Timeliness	Total Frequency
Strongly Agree	101	125	134	111	152	120	745
Agree	93	62	54	68	44	70	389
Undecided	2	6	8	12	4	10	42
Disagree	6	8	6	9	4	3	36
Strongly Disagree	3	4	3	5	1	2	18
Total	205	205	205	205	205	205	1230

Source: Questionnaire administered 2016.

Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.801 ^a	.821	.741	.76543

a. Predictors: (Constant), Enhancement, Job Knowledge, Skills, Competence and Morale.

Model		Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	104.435	5	18.465	12.435	.0021 ^a
	Residual	169.759	198	2.118		
	Total	274.194	203			

a. Predictors: (Constant), Enhancement, Job Knowledge, Skills, Competence and Morale.

b. Dependent Variable: Timeliness.

Summary of Regression Results and other Statistics

Regression	A	β_1 Enhancmnt	β_2 JobKnw	β_3 Skills	β_4 Competence	β_4 Morale
Coefficient	-1.981	0.672	0.541	0.731	0.352	1.963
P. value	0.002	0.025	0.0098	0.034	0.022	0.0011
R	0.821					
r ²	0.741					

Source: Researcher’s Computation 2016.

The regression line $Timeliness = -1.981 + 0.672Enhancement + 0.541JobKnowledge + 0.731kills + 0.352Competence + 1.963Morale$ indicates that employees’ timeliness will increase by 0.672units for every 1unit increase in Enhancement, increase by 0.541units for every 1unit increase in Job Knowledge, increase by 0.731units for every 1unit increase in Skills, increase by 0.352units for every 1unit increase in Competence, and increase by 1.963units for every 1unit increase in Morale. The significant values or P-values of 0.025, 0.0098, 0.034, 0.022, and 0.0011, in all the respective variables are less than the t-value of 0.05. We therefore reject the Null Hypothesis and accept the Alternative hypothesis, that the effect of the Training of Academic staff on employees’ Timeliness in Federal Polytechnic, Kaura Namoda is significant. This is collaborated by the correlation coefficient (r) of 0.801 that indicates a strong positive relationship. The coefficient of determination (r²) of 0.821 indicates that about 82.1% of variation on employees’ timeliness can be explained by staff training. In the absence of staff training, it is indicated that employees’ timeliness will reduce by 1.981 as shown by the constant (α). The F-Statistics value of 12.435 and its corresponding P-value of 0.0021 also collaborate the rejection of the null hypothesis that the model is fit and the effect of Training of Academic Staff on employees’ Timeliness is insignificant.

Training of Academic Staff and Employees’ Work Quality.

Table 3.2: Responses on the Training of Academic Staff and Employees’ Work Quality.

Response	Enhancement	Job Knowledge	Skills	Competence	Morale	Work Quality	Total Frequency
Strongly Agree	101	127	144	120	152	153	797
Agree	91	60	55	67	43	40	356
Undecided	4	6	4	4	5	2	25
Disagree	6	8	2	9	4	6	35
Strongly Disagree	3	4	0	5	1	4	17
Total	205	205	205	205	205	205	1230

Source: Questionnaire administered 2016.

Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.945 ^a	.934	.812	1.3432

a. Predictors: (Constant), Enhancement, Job Knowledge, Skills, Competence and Morale.

ANOVA^b

Model		Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	182.698	5	43.327	102.652	.0001 ^a
	Residual	179.375	198	1.447		
	Total	362.073	203			

a. Predictors: (Constant), Enhancement, Job Knowledge, Skills, Competence and Morale.

b. Dependent Variable: Work Quality.

Summary of Regression Results and other Statistics.

Regression	A	B ₁ Enhancmnt	B ₂ JobKnw	β ₃ Skills	β ₄ Competence	β ₄ Morale
Coefficient	-2.562	0.444	0.3423	2.342	0.343	1.334
P. value	0.000	0.002	0.021	0.030	0.005	0.010
R	0.934					
r²	0.812					

Source: Researcher’s Computation 2016.

From the above results and analyses, it is evident that, employees’ performance in terms of Productivity, Timeliness and Work quality are positively related to Training of Academic Staff with statistical significance measured by employees’ Enhancement, Job knowledge, Skills, Competence and Morale. This implies that, employees’ Productivity, Timeliness and Work quality increase with increase in Training of Academic staff such as employees’ Enhancement, Job knowledge, Skills, Competence and Morale The regression line Work Quality = -2.562 + 0.444Enhancement + 0.342JobKnowledge + 2.342Skills + 0.343Competence + 1.334Morale indicates that employees’ quality of work will increase by 0.444units for every 1unit increase in Enhancement, increase by 0.342units for every 1unit increase in Job Knowledge, increase by 2.342units for every 1unit increase in Skills, increase by 0.343 units for every 1 unit increase in Competence, and increase by 1.334units for every 1unit increase in Morale. The significant values or P-values of 0.002, 0.021, 0.030, 0.005, and 0.010, in all the respective variables are less than the t-value of 0.05. We, therefore, reject the Null hypothesis and accept the Alternative hypothesis that the effect of the Training of Academic staff on employees’ Work quality in the Federal Polytechnic, Kaura Namoda is significant. This is collaborated by the correlation coefficient (r) of 0.972 that indicates a strong positive relationship. The coefficient of determination (r²) of 0.934 indicates that about 93.4% of variation on employees’ work quality can be explained by academic staff training. In the absence of such staff training, it is indicated that employees’ work quality will reduce by 2.562 as shown by the constant (α). The F-Statistics value of 102.652 and its corresponding P-value of 0.0001 also collaborate the rejection of the Null hypothesis that the effect of the Training of Academic staff on employees’ Work quality. This is consistent with the findings in previous studies such as Harrison (2000); Wright and Geroy (2001); Swart, et al., (2005); Farooq and Aslam (2011); and more recently Sultana, et al., (2012). Furthermore, the study aligns with the theory of reinforcement that believed that training is a strategic tool to make job interesting to the workers and as the avenue for the employees to improve themselves for optimal performance, which can culminate to promoting employees for outstanding performance, innovation, and creativity as a result of the training attended. Thus, by implication, the effectiveness of training and learning depends on the pattern

of the job related knowledge, skills, capability, competencies and behavior that are important for better performance which invariably is capable of influencing organizational success.

The overall results and analyses clearly indicate that, employees' performance in terms of productivity, timeliness and work quality is positively related with the Training of Academic Staff with statistical significance measured by employees' enhancement, job knowledge, skills, competence and morale respectively. The correlation coefficient (r) indicates a strong positive relationship between the variables of the study (Training of Academic Staff and Employees' Performance). The coefficients of determination (r^2) across the variables indicate that more than 80% of variation on employees' performance can be explained by staff training. The F-statistics indicated the fitness of the model in all the respective cases.

5. Conclusion

The findings of the study revealed positive and significant effects of the Training of Academic Staff on Employees' Performance in the Federal Polytechnic, Kaura Namoda. This implies that effective academic staff training in terms of employees' enhancement, job knowledge, skills, competence, and morale, improve employees' performance in terms of productivity, timeliness, and work quality. Thus the study concludes that academic staff training in Federal Polytechnic, Kaura Namoda has a significant effect in influencing the performances of employees. In another vein with regards to the regression results and analyses it was noted that employees' morale has greater influence in ensuring effective performance in terms of productivity, timeliness and work quality to other variables used in the study. Finally, skill was found to be the second most influential variable, followed by job knowledge, competence, and enhancement respectively.

6. Recommendations

In the light of the above findings and conclusion drawn, the study recommends that:

1. Federal Polytechnic, Kaura Namoda should continue to train its academic staff in order to achieve the best performance from employees that will make the attainment of the overall objectives of the Polytechnic possible.
2. The current practice of paying trainees in bulk should be reviewed and made annually after submission of progress report to the institution. This will go a long way in minimizing inherent abuses now prevalent in the operation of training and development system in the Polytechnic.
3. Beneficiaries of training programs should be required to serve the Polytechnic for a longer period before further sponsorship is made or being allowed to leave the service.
4. Officers sponsored for part-time programs should be bonded by the polytechnic.
5. The polytechnic should endeavor to ascertain the status of the various training institutions in which its staff intend to go, before they are released for sponsorship.
6. Re-training of already trained staff should be periodically organized so as to spring up the desired employees' performance that will inspire better institutional performance and service delivery.

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